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D9.2: DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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List of Abbreviations (if necessary)

DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
CERN	The European Organization for Nuclear Research
IPRs	Intellectual Property Rights
DPO	Data Protection Officer

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Fly-Radar Data Management Plan (DMP) follows the Horizon 2020 DMP template that was designed to be applied to any Horizon 2020 project that produces, collects or process research data. The Data Management Plan describes the data management principles and strategies, tools and Fly-Radar datasets. The consortium will also aim at open access when publishing papers and articles.

The DMP is a living document to be updated as the implementation of the project progresses and when significant changes occur.

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1 Objectives and scope of the document

The Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the Fly-Radar project, as a Horizon 2020 project. The DMP aims at defining the management strategy of data generated during the project with the purpose to making research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR).

2.2 Structure of the deliverable

The document is structured following the guideline of H2020 programme on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 including the following information:

- Data Management Plan (DMP) guiding principles and strategy
- Description of Fly-Radar type of data
- Description of FAIR DATA characteristics including DMP Review Process
- Allocation of resources
- Data Security
- Ethical Aspects
- Conclusions

3. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

The Fly-Radar Data Management Plan (DMP) aims to provide a strategy for managing key data generated and collected during the project and optimize access to and re-use of research data. The DMP is intended to be a ‘living’ document that will outline how the Fly-Radar research data will be handled during and after the project, and so it will be reviewed and updated whether necessary.

All European Union funded projects must try to disseminate as much information as possible and on top of that the Fly-Radar project adhered to the “Open Research Data Pilot”, committing to give open access to data generated during the project unless it goes against

legitimate interests. In this regard, the main purpose of the DMP is to ensure the accessibility and intelligibility of the data generated during the Fly-Radar project in order to comply with the Guidelines of the “Open Research Data Pilot”.

Each data set created during the project will be assessed and categorized as open or restricted by the owners of the content of the dataset.

All the data sets, regardless of their categorization, will be stored in each of the participant entities databases and in the Fly-Radar Cloud folders created as internal database and communication tool for the partners. In addition, those categorized as open will be publicly shared (in the case of embargo, after the embargo period is over) through the public section of the project website and ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/>).

ZENODO is an open access repository for all fields of science that allows uploading any kind of data file formats, which is recommended by the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE).

3.1 Data Management Plan (DMP) guiding principles

The Data Management Plan of Fly-Radar is realized within the Work Package 9.

The Fly-Radar project data management plan follows the principle of Open Access according to the Horizon 2020 guideline summarized in the diagram here below.

Figure 1. Open access to research data and publication decision diagram (from Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020)

The others main principles for the Fly-Radar project DPM are the following:

- ➔ This Data Management Plan (DMP) has been prepared by taking into account the template of the “Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020”
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf
- ➔ The DMP is an official project Deliverable (D9.2) due in Month 6 (July 2021), but it will be updated throughout the project, whether necessary. The first initial version will evolve depending on significant changes arising and periodic reviews at relevant reporting stages of the project.
- ➔ The consortium complies with the requirements of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). Guidance on how these regulations interact with open-access data policy can be found here: <https://www.openaire.eu/ordp/>
- ➔ Type of data, storage, confidentiality, ownership, management of intellectual property and access: procedures that will be implemented for data collection, storage, access, sharing policies, protection, retention and destruction will be in line with EU standards as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

3.2 Fly-Radar Data Management strategy

As a project participating in the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) in Horizon 2020, the Data Management strategy of the Fly-Radar project is focused on the observation of FAIR (Findable, Accessible Interoperable and Reusable) Data Management Protocols. This document addresses for each data set collected, processed and/or generated in the project the following elements:

Dataset reference and name: Internal project Identifier for the dataset to be produced. This will follow the format:

➔ **PName_PartnerName_DatasetName_Version__DateOfStorage,**

where the project name is Fly-Radar, the Partner Name represents the name of the data custodian (WP Lead/ Task Leader).

Dataset description: description of the data generated or collected, including its origin (in cases where data is collected), nature and scale, to whom it could be useful, the potential for reuse.

Standards and metadata: reference to existing suitable standards. If these do not exist, an outline on how and what metadata will be created.

Data sharing: description of how data will be shared, including access procedures, embargo periods (if any), outlines of technical mechanisms for dissemination and necessary software and other tools for enabling reuse, and definition of whether access will be open or restricted to specific groups. Identification of the repository where data will be stored, if already existing and identified, indicating the type of repository (institutional, standard repository for the discipline, etc.). In cases where the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons

for this will be stated (e.g. ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related).

Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup): description of the procedures to be put in place for long-term preservation of the data, including an indication of how long the data should be preserved, the approximate end volume, associated costs, and how these are planned to be covered.

3.3 Fly-Radar type of data

Among project datasets and deliverables, the following categories of outputs are declared “public” and will be made “Open Access” (to be provided free of charge for public sharing). These will be included in the Open Research Data Pilot and thus be managed according to the present DMP:

- Project deliverables, except those relative to WP3 and 4 that are confidential
- Articles published in Open Access scientific journal
- Conference and Workshop abstracts/articles/minutes
- Summer schools reports/documents/minutes
- Research data:
 - ✓ Mars surface and terrestrial analogues dataset (WP1)
 - ✓ System requirements dataset (WP2)
 - ✓ Design and manufacturing radar (WP3)
 - ✓ Design and manufacturing drone dataset (WP4)
 - ✓ Model qualification campaign dataset (WP5)
 - ✓ Validation and test field campaign (WP6)

3.4 Data Summary

Research data summary tables are available in Annex 1.

4. FAIR DATA

The following rules and principles, as identified and described in the present section 4, apply to all datasets identified in Annex 1 of this DMP.

4.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Metadata is data on the research data themselves. It enables other researchers to find data in an online repository and is, as such, essential for the reusability of the dataset. By adding rich and detailed metadata, other researchers, can better determine whether the dataset is relevant and useful for their own research. Metadata (type of data, location, etc.) will be

uploaded in a standardized form. This metadata will be kept separate from the original raw research data.

As described in the project Grant Agreement (Article 29.2), the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication must include all of the following:

- the terms “Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions”;
- the project name, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date and, if applicable, length of embargo period
- a persistent identifier

Fly-Radar open data will be collected in an open online research data repository: ZENODO. Its repository structure, facilities and management are in compliance with FAIR data principles as it allows researchers to deposit both publications and data, providing tools to linking them to these through persistent identifiers and data citations. ZENODO is set up to facilitate the finding, accessing, re-using and interoperating of data sets, which are the basic principles that ORDP projects must comply with. Zenodo repository is provided by OpenAIRE and hosted by CERN. Zenodo is a catch-all repository that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to:

- Share research results in a wide variety of formats including text, spreadsheets, audio, video, and images across all fields of science.
- Display their research results and get credited by making the research results citable and integrating them into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission.
- Easily access and reuse shared research results.
- Integrate their research outputs with the OpenAIRE portal.

Search keywords

Zenodo allows to perform simple and advanced search queries on Zenodo using the keywords. Zenodo also provides a user guide with easy-to-understand examples.

Naming conventions

Files and folders at data repositories will be versioned and structured by using a name convention consisting as follow: Fly-radar_Dx.y_YYYYMMDD_Vzz.doc

Version numbers

Individual file names will contain version numbers that will be incremented at each revision (Vzz).

4.2 Making data openly accessible & data sharing

In order to maximise the impact of Fly-Radar research data, the results are shared within and beyond the consortium. Selected data and results will be shared with the scientific community and other stakeholders through publications in scientific journals and presentations at conferences, as well as through open access data repositories.

The Fly-Radar project datasets are first stored and organized in a database by the data owners (personal computer, or on the institutional secure server) and on the project cloud (a restricted area of the project website). All data are made available for verification and re-use, unless the task leader declares that the data cannot be made openly accessible, for a specified reason (e.g., commercial use, patenting, other IPR protection).

To protect the copyright of the project knowledge, Creative Commons license will be used in some cases.

The Fly-Radar deliverables with the dissemination level “public” (data access policy unrestricted) will be accessible through:

- Fly-Radar project web site
- Partners database
- OpenAIRE
- ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org>) for ORDP data and datasets
- Open access journals

All data deposited on ZENODO are accessible without restrictions. For other data, potential users must contact the IPR team or the data owner in order to gain access. If necessary, appropriate IPR procedures (such as non-disclosure agreement) will be used.

4.3 Making data interoperable

Partners will observe OpenAIRE guidelines for online interoperability, including OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories, OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives, OpenAIRE Guidelines for CRIS Managers based on CERIF-XML. These guidelines can be found at: <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>.

Partners will also ensure that Fly-Radar data observes FAIR data principles under H2020 open-access policy:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-datamgt_en.pdf

In order to ensure the interoperability, all datasets will use the same standards for data and metadata capture/creation.

As the project progresses and data is more precisely identified and collected, further information on how data will be made interoperable may be further outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP, whether necessary. In particular, further information may be added on data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodology to follow to facilitate interoperability and whether the project uses standard vocabulary for all data types to allow interdisciplinary interoperability.

4.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

Each research institute is currently assessing how to license data to permit the widest reuse possible and clearly identify any requirements for data embargo and length of time for which the data will remain usable, if applicable.

All Fly-Radar project results that are open to use for any purpose will be appropriately licensed using open licensing policy (see <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/?lang=en>).

Unless required by the Consortium Agreement or specific IPRs, all Fly-Radar data products openly accessible will be discoverable (i.e., via metadata harvesting access) in reasonable time after data collection and/or generation. Default time for this will be 6 (six) months from the end of the result generation.

For datasets deposited on a public data repository (ZENODO) the access is unlimited.

Restrictions on re-use policy are applied for all protected data (see Figure 1: Open access to research data and publication decision diagram), whose re-use will be limited to the project partners.

Other restrictions could include:

- ➔ the “embargo” period imposed by journals publication policy (Green Open access);
- ➔ some or all of the following restrictions may be applied with Creative Commons licensing of the dataset:
 - ✓ Attribution: requires users of the dataset to give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
 - ✓ NonCommercial: prohibits the use of the dataset for commercial purposes by others.
 - ✓ ShareAlike: requires the others to use the same license as the original on all derivative works based on the original data.

The project data will remain re-usable for at least 1 year.

4.5 DMP Review Process

As indicated in the project management plan, internal evaluation processes will be held throughout the entire project duration to assess project data and products quality. An internal peer review is also set forth for project deliverables quality assurance.

Internal processes of quality assurance are envisaged in the Project Management Plan, available on the project website. Results will be analysed and collected throughout the entire duration of the project. In this regard, the communication and dissemination activities will be constantly reported in the dedicated section of the EU continuous reporting portal.

Further updates of the Data Management Plan will be released if necessary, including eventual updates of the online research data repository, where data are collected and shared among partners.

5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Costs related to open-access to research data in Horizon 2020 are eligible for reimbursement under the conditions defined in the H2020 Grant Agreement, in particular Article 6 and Article 6.2.D.3, but also other articles relevant for the cost category chosen. Project

beneficiaries will be responsible for applying for reimbursement for costs related to making data accessible to others beyond the consortium.

The costs for making data FAIR includes:

- Data set storage, management and maintenance costs: these costs will be considered as institutional costs and incurred by Coordinator's Project Office, who will be also responsible for it
- Fees associated with the publication of scientific articles containing project's research data in "Gold" or "Green" Open access journals:
 - ✓ Any fee incurred for Open Access through scientific publication of the data will be under the responsibility of the data owner (authors)-partner(s). The cost sharing will be applied in case of multiple authors.
- Project Website operation: to be determined
- Data archiving at ZENODO and on other on-line data base: free of charge
- Copyright licensing with Creative Commons: free of charge
- Patenting or other IP protection: this cost will be incurred by the author (s) applying for the IP protection.

The project members of General Assembly are also responsible of the Data Management of Fly-Radar dataset and research data in accordance with each organization internal Data Protection Officers (DPO).

Each partner is responsible for the data they produce.

6. DATA SECURITY

The following guidelines will be followed in order to ensure the security of the data:

- Store data in at least two separate locations to avoid loss of data;
- Encrypt data if it is deemed necessary by the participating researchers;
- Limit the use of USB flash drives.
- Label files in a systematically structured way in order to ensure the coherence of the final dataset.

All project deliverables and data will be stored and shared in the project cloud set up on the project website, which is restricted to the project consortium. As an initial step, only the Consortium Partners will have access to the cloud storage where dataset and metadata are filed. Following scientific publications and articles, the dataset deliverables and the final research results that do not hold a restrict access for commercial/patent/IP purposes will be shared through ZENODO and other database to promote the making data FAIR.

7. ETHICAL ASPECTS

Data sets collected or generated in Fly-radar do not raise ethics concerns. No personal information will be collected and/or generated in the frame of the Fly-Radar project.

8. CONCLUSIONS

This document describes the main principles and guidelines for the Data Management for the Fly-Radar project, along with the description of the dataset that will be generated/processed. As a living document, it will be updated throughout the project lifetime where necessary.

9. ANNEX 1: RESEARCH DATA SUMMARY TABLES

Dataset N.	1	WP1
Dataset Name	Fly-Radar_ UCBL_MarsSurface&TerrestrialAnalogues_v1_date	
Lead Beneficiary	Partner 4: UCBL	
Open/ Restricted	Open	
Purpose of data	<p>Mars surface data will be collected/processed for the analysis of the major factors affecting the survey campaign of Mars. It will deal with modelling and simulation of the Mars environment, SAR images and subsurface data, this way unravelling possible impact of individual and combined parameters on the outcome of the measurement operation of the radar data.</p> <p>This multidisciplinary effort will deal with rock and soil composition, environment, geological setting, and regolith density.</p> <p>Terrestrial Analogue data will be collected for the definition of the test ranges, including the analysis of the test ranges in Morocco, Afar and Botswana. Data will be relative to sedimentary environments, volcanic edifices, stratigraphy, subsurface data, rock density, dielectric constants and other physical and petro-physical parameters.</p>	
Data Types:	<p>Bibliography -> investigation of what has been already done</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → text (e.g. reports) → numeric (e.g. tables) → audiovisual (e.g. image) → simulated (e.g. model) <p>Remote sensing Images -> to study the geology and geophysics of investigated areas</p> <p>Simulation of Radargramms-> to evaluate the potential of the FlyRadar system to investigate Martian and Earth subsurface</p>	
Data format:	<p>Bibliography -> pdf</p> <p>Remote sensing data -> he5, tiff, shp, grd, pds, raw</p> <p>Simulation -> raw</p>	
New/ Existing data	<p>Bibliography -> yes</p> <p>Remote sensing -> yes</p>	

	Simulation-> no
Size	Bibliography : 100 Mo Remote sensing 1 To Simulation 100Go
Data origin	Bibliography-> compiled by staff from web sources Remote sensing -> compiled from web sources managed by space agencies Simulation -> from numerical solvers of Maxwell equations
Reference of canonical (links)	http://global-data.mars.asu.edu/bin/ctx.pl https://land.copernicus.eu/imagery-in-situ http://global-data.mars.asu.edu/bin/hirise.pl https://urs.earthdata.nasa.gov
Dataset is	Growing and revisable
Data value	Researchers Simulation -> long term use (5 years)

Dataset N.	2	WP2
Dataset Name	Fly-Radar_UCBL_System requirements_v1_date	
Lead Beneficiary	Partner 4: UCBL	
Open/ Restricted	Open	
Purpose of data	Data will be collected/processed for the definition of system requirements of the instrument suitable for planetary exploration, in term of mass budget, power budget (including TL assessment vs power consumption), thermal analysis, mechanical and data processing requirements.	
Data Types: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → text (e.g. reports) → numeric (e.g. tables) → audiovisual (e.g. image) → simulated (e.g. model) 	Bibliography -> investigation of what has been already done	
Data format:	pdf	
New/ Existing data	Existing data	
Size	100 Mo	
Data origin	Bibliography-> compiled by staff from web sources	
Reference of canonical (links)	isiwebofscience	
Dataset is	Growing and revisable	
Data Value	Staff only	

Dataset N.	3	WP3
Dataset Name	Fly-Radar_CORISTA_Design&ManufacturingRadar_v1_date	
Lead Beneficiary	Partner 6: CO.RI.S.T.A.	
Open/ Restricted	Restricted due to commercial use and possible patent application	
Purpose of data	<p>Data will be processed/generated for building the multi-mode, low-frequency radar for drone installation.</p> <p>Data will be relative to the Radar design, focusing on system miniaturisation and radar data processing definition and development.</p>	
Data Types: → text (e.g. reports) → numeric (e.g. tables) → audiovisual (e.g. image) → simulated (e.g. model)	Text Numeric Simulated	
Data format:	pdf, doc, txt Binary with internal format, Matlab	
New/ Existing data	Existing data New for experimental data	
Size	Various	
Data origin	experimental simulation derived/compiled	
Reference of canonical (links)	IEEE library	
Dataset is	Growing: new data may be added, but the old data is never changed or deleted.	
Data Value	Academic researchers and industry	

Dataset N.	4	WP4
Dataset Name	Fly_Radar_HYPERION_Design&ManufacturingDrone_v1_date	
Lead Beneficiary	Partner 5: HYPERION SEVEN	
Open/ Restricted	Restricted due to commercial use and possible patent application	
Purpose of data	<p>Data will be processed/generated for dimensioning and building of the drone system.</p> <p>In particular data will be relative to dimensioning the 3 segments (Aerial, Cable segment, Ground segment) and to the final test of the system, including different component e.g. Aerial segment, Ground/air link control of radar and data drone (by the fiber optic), and ground station.</p>	
Data Types: → text (e.g. reports) → numeric (e.g. tables) → audiovisual (e.g. image) → simulated (e.g. model)	Text: report /manual Numeric: flight data Audio-visual: image /video	
Data format:	PDF/ TXT/CSV/JPG/ TIFF/MP4/MOV/AVI/ KML/SHP	
New/ Existing data	New	
Size	TBD	
Data origin	User and maintenance manual of the drone System operating procedures manual (Standard Operational Procedure)	
Reference of canonical (links)	N/A	

Dataset is	GROWING
Data value	Project partners Not known yet the potential value of long-term reuse of the data

Dataset N.	5	WP5
Dataset Name	Fly-Radar_CBKPAN_ModelQualificationCampaign_v1_date	
Lead Beneficiary	Partner 2: CBK PAN	
Open/ Restricted	Open	
Purpose of data	<p>Data will be processed for the identification of a technology development roadmap for planetary exploration and Earth Science.</p> <p>Data will be relative to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • radar calibration and instruments performance • software update to acquire and analyse the data 	
Data Types: → text (e.g. reports) → numeric (e.g. tables) → audiovisual (e.g. image) → simulated (e.g. model)	- Data generated by WPs 3 and 4 - New data collected during the campaign	
Data format:	Anticipated to be similar to the data generated during WPs 3 and 4D	
New/ Existing data	New	
Size	TBD	
Data origin	FlyRadar technical measurements	
Reference of canonical (links)	Not identified to date	

Dataset is	Fixed
Data Value	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Primarily, internal use for the project.- Might be of use for other projects, such as application to an equivalent instrument onboard a planetary lander.

Dataset N.	6	WP6
Dataset Name	Fly-Radar_IRSPS_Validation&TestFieldCampaign_v1_date	
Lead Beneficiary	Partner 1: IRSPS srl	
Open/ Restricted	Open	
Purpose of data	<p>Data will generated to test the performance, operations and scientific results of the Fly-Radar system. This verification process will be composed of a large number of end-to-end tests, as well as of subsystem checks.</p> <p>The test ranges will be located in dry desert environments in order to take advantage of a stronger penetration of the radar signal. The field test will also test the scientific results comparing other data sets with the data obtained during the FlyRadar operations. The latter will be also analysed. Both the radar performance and the operational procedures will be tested and evaluated.</p>	
Data Types: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → text (e.g. reports) → numeric (e.g. tables) → audiovisual (e.g. image) → simulated (e.g. model) 	<p>Bibliography and Technical Manuals: Collection of previous investigations and state of the art. The data will be stored mainly in PDF format (Portable Document Format).</p> <p>Technical reports about operations: Textual and numerical reports. The data will be stored as PDF, DOC or XLS depending to the data type.</p> <p>Remote sensing data: Resulting from geological and geophysical investigations. The files will be stored in GeoTiff, HDF HE5, SHP, PDS, GRD, RAW, JPG, PNG, DAT, SDAT formats.</p> <p>Point Cloud Data: Resulting from photogrammetric surveys to support investigations. The file format will be XYZ and LAS.</p> <p>Dissemination media: Audiovisual contents for the dissemination and promotion of the project, both in image and video format.</p>	
Data format:	<p>Text files: TXT, PDF, DOC.</p> <p>Spreadsheet: XLS, CSV.</p> <p>Raster Data: GeoTiff, HDF HE5, PDS, GRD, RAW, JPG, PNG,</p>	

	<p>DAT, SDAT.</p> <p>Vector data: SHP.</p> <p>Point cloud data: XYZ, LAS.</p> <p>Video format: MP4, AVI.</p> <p>Audio format: MP3, WAVE.</p>
New/ Existing data	Everything new except for data templates and pre-existing bibliography data.
Size	<p>Bibliography, Manual, Reports: 1-200 MB</p> <p>Remote sensing and Photogrammetry data: 1-1000 GB</p> <p>Media: 1MB - 1GB</p>
Data origin	<p>Experimental: Radargramms, Point Cloud</p> <p>Observational: Remote sensing data, satellite sensor readings, drone images</p> <p>Derived/Compiled: Vector data, table contents, reports</p>
Reference of canonical (links)	N/A
Dataset is	Growing
Data value	Researchers in Remote Sensing and Radar ambit, Industry with interests in Radar uses, Earth Observing educational institutions, Space Agencies (Payload Planning and development).

10. ANNEX 2: DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN TABLE TEMPLATE

Dataset N.	X	WP Y
Dataset Name	Fly-Radar_Institution_WP_v1_date	
Lead Beneficiary	Partner X: Name of Partner	
Open/ Restricted	Open/restricted	
Purpose of data		
Data Types: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → text (e.g. reports) → numeric (e.g. tables) → audiovisual (e.g. image) → simulated (e.g. model) 		Describe the type of data used or generated within the project, specifying the form and format of the data.
Data format:		Examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → plain text, (txt), HTML, XLM, PDF/A ... → tables, .XLSX, .CSV ... → images, JPEG, .JPG, .PNG, .TIFF, AIFF, WAVE, .MP3, .MP4...
New/ Existing data		Indicate if you re-use existing data (generated outside the Fly-Radar project). If so, explain how.
Size		In MB/GB
Data origin		Describe the source /origin of your data E.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → <u>experimental</u> (i.e. chromatograms, magnetic fields readings...)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → <u>observational</u> (i.e. sensor readings, images, telemetries, sample data...) → <u>simulation</u> (i.e. climate models, economic models, materials models, ...) → <u>derived/compiled</u> (i.e. the results of text and data mining, compiled databases..)
<p>Reference of canonical (links)</p>		<p>E.g. indicate the collection or conglomeration of smaller (peer-reviewed) datasets published and curated - i.e. chemical structures, gene sequence databanks, spatial data portals..</p>
<p>Dataset is</p>		<p>Indicate if it is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Fixed: never change after being collected or generated. → Growing: new data may be added, but the old data is never changed or deleted. → Revisable: new data may be added, and old data may be changed or deleted.
<p>Data value</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Describe to whom the data could be useful (e.g. researchers, academy, industry, etc.) → Estimate potential value of long-term reuse of the data

END OF DOCUMENT

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